

Leveraging AI for Public Health: Monitoring Children's Exposure to Digital Marketing of Unhealthy Products on Social Media

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Problem

Need for effective tools to monitor and enforce marketing restrictions

Lack of parent's awareness of the potential risks associated with certain advertisements

KidAd Project

“KidAd is a comprehensive set of monitoring tools designed to capture screenshots and metadata from interactive digital media sources. It utilises AI-assisted algorithms to accurately identify both direct and indirect advertisements and brand promotions related to unhealthy foods.”

By Special Initiative on NCDs and Innovation, WHO Regional Office for Europe

KidAd Data Collector

Set of tools to monitor, capture, and store digital interactions on children's devices

KidAd Data Analyser

Advanced AI/ML algorithm to analyse the captured data

KidAd Data Browser

Navigate through the collected data, review AI predictions, and conduct searches based on specific criteria

A-ALGO contribution to KidAd Project

- Design and Development of KidAd Android App
- Build Server AI Pipeline Using A-ALGO's cloud-based data pipeline tool "ArgusOculus"
- Train Server Image Labeling, Brand Recognition, and Advertisement Detection AI Models
- In-app AI-assisted filtering for Removing Explicit Images and Sensitive Data

Version 2

- An AI tool was introduced, which can be trained to detect unhealthy food products and brands
- The AI tool uses the cloud-based data pipeline tool "ArgusOculus" to develop and train AI models with minimal tech effort and resources
- The pipeline contains two main stages:
 - Natural language Processing (NLP) models extract text from the screenshot and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models label the screenshot and describe its content
- Power BI dashboard to submerge results

High-Level Architecture

A-ALGO Pipeline

 Image Labeling

 Object Detection

 Text Extraction

 Entity & Insight Extraction

 Brand Recognition

Screenshot Classification

Process each screenshot via a set of AI algorithms

Initially to try to clear out unwanted screenshots (e.g..... Containing apps that we didn't monitor, messages)

Use our own AI models to classify screenshots

Optionally use third-party image classification services (Google / Microsoft)

Combine all classification results and store them in cloud storage (JSON data)

Training AI Model

1. Select a category:

- Promotion Private data Age-Inappropriate Other

2. Select one or more labels:

- Adult content Sensitive data Dangerous activity
 Smoking or drugs Food Promotion
 People Contain a Brand Unhealthy food
 Fast food

3. Remove unrelated text related to image displayed below or add a text for the image:

Enter Text ADD

Buscar	X
Reels	X
PEZZAPROUEICA	X
Sin cerUos	X
SI ESTAS A DIETA	X
lorenaonfit	X
Seguir	X

Brand Identification

The image shows a video player interface with a brand identification tool overlay. The video player has a top bar with navigation controls (play, stop, back, forward, full screen, info, filters) and a progress bar showing 0 seconds. The video content is a vertical stack of three frames from a YouTube video. The first frame shows french fries with a 2:07 timestamp. The second frame shows a KFC bucket of chicken with a 22:39 timestamp. The third frame shows a KFC burger and other food items with a 15:41 timestamp. A red and white KFC logo is overlaid on the third frame, with a label 'KFC 1 (MANUAL)' pointing to it. The right side of the interface shows a panel with 'Objects', 'Labels', and 'Issues' tabs. The 'Objects' tab is active, showing two objects: '1 RECTANGLE SHAPE kfc' and '2 RECTANGLE SHAPE kfc'. The 'Appearance' section is expanded, showing 'Color by' (Label, Instance, Group), 'Opacity' (0), 'Selected opacity' (0), and checkboxes for 'Outlined borders' and 'Show bitmap'.

Menu Save Undo Redo 164237.png 0 Fullscreen Info Filters Standard

Objects Labels Issues

Sort by ID - as...

1 RECTANGLE SHAPE kfc

2 RECTANGLE SHAPE kfc

Appearance

Color by Label Instance Group

Opacity

Selected opacity

Outlined borders Show bitmap Show projections

Evde aşk ile hamburger nasıl yapılır
Mayda Şirin · 13 views · 23 hours ago

KFC Burger & 20 LEG PIECE BUCKET CHALLENGE !! With BLOOPERS
DAN JR VLOGS · 1M views · 3 years ago

KFC 1 (MANUAL)

Kid Ad

- **Step 1** : The monitored app takes the Screenshot
- **Step 2** : Extract text and analyse image using AI/ML
- **Text**
 - ["folger", "for", "chefkoudy", "how much cheesel sauce vou like", "on a", "burgere", "#ch_", "vis mer", "s the hard knock life", "hjem", "venner", "innboks", "deg"]
- **Labels**
 - ["hamburger", "person", "human face", "hamburger", "hamburger"]

Kid Ad

"keyphrases" : evde aşk ile hamburger 20 leg piece bucket dan jr vlogs il yapilir
1m views3 french fries fast food kfc burger cuisine poster meal mayda
şirin bloopers home shorts subscriptions cd library snack cc rfc
34

Translated text: [fast food, food, cuisine, poster, meal, 3:34 d, evde aşk ile hamburger nasıl yapılır, mayda şirin 13 views 23 hours ago, kfc burger & 20 leg piece bucket, challenge !! with bloopers, dan jr vlogs 1m views3 years ago, home, kfc, shorts, subscriptions, 2:07, cd, 22:39, 15:41, library, french fries, snack, cc, dan jr vlogs, im views, rfc]

Masked text: [fast food, food, cuisine, poster, meal, 3:34 d, evde aşk ile hamburger nasıl yapılır, ***** 13 views 23 hours ago, kfc burger & 20 leg piece bucket, challenge !! with bloopers, ***** vlogs 1m views3 years ago, home, kfc, shorts, subscriptions, 2:07, cd, 22:39, 15:41, library, ***** , snack, cc, ***** vlogs, im views, rfc]

AI & Security

⚠ Sensitive data leak

⚠ PII in images

⚠ Harder to control different levels of permission on LLM based search

⚠ Database

⚠ Infrastructure & DevOps

Lesson learned

 Multiple agent-based pipeline

 Deployment of AI containers

 Design for both Cloud & On-Premises

Thank You

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